

THOUGHTS OF THE ORIGIN OF MINOAN CIVILIZATION

Overviews and conclusions

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Abstract

The article, in preparation for paleographic research, reviews the already encyclopedically accepted and recent results of several relevant scientific disciplines to delimit the temporal, geographic, and civilizational relationships of the formation of Minoan civilization from the assumptions of the Sumerian Origin Theory. He concludes that the archaic Sumerian population that flourished civilization c. 3100 BC moved to South, Southwest Anatolia, where they lived with the Luwi people for c. 900 years, then around 2200 BC they settled on the Cyclades, Thera, and Crete, forming a palace farming system, transforming the social system of the neolithic natives, bringing in more advanced agriculture, crafts, and extensive maritime trade. He states that the Minoan writing systems are the descendants of a proto-writing created as a result of a coevolution took place in a Luwi environment, conveying an archaic Sumerian language. By reinterpreting a number of oddities, he hypothesizes that the power center of the Minoan world was in fact Thera. The confirmation of this assumption related to Crete, would clarify many open question so far.

Keywords

Minoan, Crete, Thera, Sumer Origin Theory (SOT), Uruk Origin Theory, Luwian theory, luwi connection, Cretan hieroglyphic, Linear-A

Preface

Choosing the methods of a paleographic algorithm to express metric similarity is a very sophisticated method. The resulting metric is a mathematical result, an aid to expressing a visual similarity, but it is by no means certain that this result indicates a true historical relationship. Too many subject contexts can lead to completely erroneous results that are incompatible with those of other disciplines because of the degree of distortion and noise of the similarity measurement. Therefore, the number of sets to be included in a paleographic study should be limited as much as possible. This delimitation has to be done in historical time, in geographical space and in the system of civilization relations.

1. Introduction

Numerous assumptions and theories about the origin of the Cretan, Minoan population, and civilization have emerged from the early 20th century to the turn of the millennium, from African origin to Mesopotamian and other relationships. However, with the advent of new archeogenetic technologies in the millennium, important results concerning the genetic relations of the Minoans were explored, exploring the origin of European agricultural civilizations. From 2013 to 2017 (S. Selier, J. H. Hughey, P. Paschou, E. Callaway, B. Yirka, M. Slatkin, J. B. Pereira, J. Amos, G. Stamatoyannopoulos, I. Lazaridis, J. Krause, J. Ramsdin), more and more research teams have carried out archeogenetic research with increasing numbers of specimens, and the initial Western Anatolia and then Southwest Anatolian relations have shifted towards Southeastern Anatolia and Mesopotamia.

Marija Gimbutas introduced the idea of "ancient European" in her books, published first in 1974 (*The Goddesses and Gods of Old Europe*), then in 1989 (*The Language of the Goddess*) and 1991 (*The*

Civilization of the Goddess), which caused very heated professional debates¹. According to her, around 7000 BC an early agriculture population of Anatolian origin settled in what is now Europe, where they were mixed with an already there living Neolithic hunter-gathering indigenous population, so forming the "old European" (eteo european) population, whose groups have for thousands of years (i.e. 6500-3500) scattered, but similar and unified culture and they lived in non-organized, relatively peaceful rural communities. These cultures of at the end the Bronze Age and at the beginning of the Iron Age were destroyed by the Indo-European, steppe, warlike "kurgan cultures" and acquired dominance over them.

Inspired by this, later David Rohl (among others) in his book (Legend: The Genesis of Civilization, London, Arrow Books 1998), suggested that Minoan civilization may have been influenced or derived from the Sumerian / Mesopotamian civilization a thousand years earlier.

In parallel with these antecedents, the 'Sumerian Origin' / origin hypothesis for the origin of the Cretan hieroglyphs (CH) and protolinear (CP) scripts (Haarmann - 1996, Filippou - 2014, Papakitsos, Kenanidis - 2016) is supported by archeogenetic results, and the "Sumer Origin Theory" (SOT²), the origin theory of Minoan civilization is also developed.

In the following, I will try to summarize the facts and ideas that reinforce the truth of this theory in order to set paleographic goals.

Article structure:

- In section 2, I consider recent archeogenetic results those identify the large population migrations.
- In section 3, I will first highlight the encyclopedic knowledge that is important to us with regard to the Aegean, southern Mesopotamian, and southern and southwestern Anatolia, and then consider the latest research findings.
- In section 4, I summarize and reconcile the conclusions outlined in section 3.

2. Overview of recent archeogenetic results

In the early 2000s, archeogenetic was revived by the use of new genetic techniques in archeology. This made it a very effective tool for archeology and civilization research. It is not uncritically applicable, but it points to the biological relationship, intermingling, and longer, shorter cohabitation of individuals, groups, populations that have ever lived, which may or may not mean cultural contact. The genetic sample used may be from archaeological samples as well as from contemporary specimens.

2.1. First results for ancient Crete and Mycenae

From the early researches of the 2000s, the first major press releases were published in 2013. The authors (Jeffery R. Hughey et al) of article [2] immediately decided a debate between two old competing theories, based on 4800-3700 year old samples:

- The first Cretan immigrants from Anatolia came 9,000 years ago during the time of the "agricultural explosion", which simultaneously refutes the hypothesis of North African origin and all other origins.
- The current population of Crete has a close genetic proximity to ancient samples, meaning that the genetic features of the population has hardly changed in 4800-3700 years, meaning that later settlers were either small in number or represented near haplotypes.

Considering that the first Neolithic population reached Crete c. 9,000 years ago, coinciding with the migration of Neolithic agricultural culture from Anatolia, it is very likely that the same ancient

¹ The fiercely controversial charge of feminism was sparked in particular by the book "The Civilization of the Goddess" (1991), in which she stated that these civilizations were Goddess and woman-centered ("gynocentric") as opposed to Bronze Age Indo-European patriarchal ("androcratic") cultures.

² In what follows, we will consider this theory in a more general sense, such as the "Mesopotamian origin theory".

population that settled in Europe spread to Crete and contributed to the early Minoan civilization. This result seems to confirm M. Gimbutas's earlier theory.

The author (Stephanie Seiler) of article [3] notes that Neolithic European and Cretan immigration came from the eastern Anatolian regions, and even from the Middle East.

The author (Ewen Callaway) of article [4], referring to Wolfgang Haak, a molecular archaeologist at the University of Adelaide in Australia, thinks that Crete's early history is likely to be more complex, as several Neolithic populations may have arrived at different times.

In 2014, the authors (Peristera Paschou et al) of the study [5] made several important statements:

- The Neolithic populations that colonized Europe about 9000 years ago were believed to have migrated from the Middle East to Anatolia and thence to Central Europe via Thrace and the Balkans, but they believed that the alternative route was the "island hopping" technique along the southern European coastline³ not including crossing the Bosphorus⁴.
- They exclude the Levant route, which was also a widespread alternative hypothesis.
- From the Mediterranean, sailing men bring their genes and agricultural knowledge first, while in other regions of Europe the entire population migrates and mixes with glacial gathering-fishing-hunting populations.

2.2 Recent results, with respect to ancient Crete and Mycenae

In 2017, several research teams, partly in co-operation, published new results correcting previous studies. The subject of these studies is the settlement of the whole of Europe, but some findings also concern Crete and the Aegean.

For example, in an article published by Proceedings of the Royal Society B in 2017 [6], the authors (Joana B. Pereira et al) make several new, very significant findings:

- In the early settlement of Europe, two major waves can be distinguished from the Middle East, Anatolia. During the Late Glacial Period (c. 18000-11000 BP), there was an influx into the Aegean and the Eastern Central Mediterranean, which may have been primarily a gathering-fishing-hunter group, but in the latter period their initial agricultural knowledge was not excluded⁵. The Iberian, Central, North, and Western European settlement (c. 9000-8000 BP) is connect to clearly a Neolithic "agricultural

³ Migration along the northern coast of the Black Sea is neither refuted nor claimed for lack of patterns (probably due to unfortunate political conditions), which - on the one hand would simply explain the Caucasian admixture of Mycenaean, and its Indo-European language and later arrival than the Minoan, - on the other hand for European immigration would justify a very likely route to the north from Carpathians.

⁴ This claim, the exclusion the crossing of the Bosphorus Strait, or the bypass of the Black Sea in the northern region is not substantiated as samples from this region were not included in the investigation. Mycenae, a second settlement with Indo-European features, is most likely imagined from this region, namely this would explain why while the Minoans, as the first settlers, dominated the archipelago around Crete, but their relatives, the Mycenaean conquered today's Greek mainland and could not extend to the islands, which are dominated by the Minoans. The first Minoans could already have significant shipping experience due to the settling of the sea, while the Mycenaean population on the land could not yet have it. Assuming not two, but at least three large waves of migration, the younger age of the archaeological finds in the Eastern Balkans justify a later settlement which was no longer southward, as it was already hindered by the Mycenaean settlement. Archaeological excavations in the Eastern Balkans and Crimea are still in their early stages and may be another reason for the lack of evidence.

⁵ In the Mediterranean, finding suitable samples for analysis is a major problem and a source of uncertainty.

explosion", which coincide with previous results. Assimilation of the glacial and Neolithic populations shows geographically different genetic ratios.

- Importantly, their further observation is that c. 5,000 BP the influx of tribes from the steppe and Caucasian regions gradually suppresses the glacial-neolithic genetic heritage on varying degrees. Thus, climatic influences, overpopulation, and the immigration of militant, primarily Indo-European peoples, trigger conflicts over the possession of resources, and the peaceful "original Europe" of Gimbutas for 3000-4000 years is eradicated by history. Fortified settlements appear, traces of weapons and armed conflicts are found, and fertility cults and goddesses are replaced by warring gods.

In article [7], I. Lazaridis et al., confirm that Minoans and Mycenaeans are genetically approx. 75% identical. Both populations are from Southeastern Anatolia. The Minoans reached the Aegean through Southwestern Anatolia, and the Mycenaeans through a more northerly route (see above). The remainder of the genome is 25% Caucasian (Armenian) and Iranian. Mycenaeans, however, also have Siberian (Western Eurasia) and Eastern European descent. Modern Greeks and Cretans are clearly descendants of their ancestors, of course, with the "dilution" that has occurred in modern history. Other key issues are: - the relationship of this two groups and the Caucasian, - the explanation of the Indo-European character of the Mycenaeans, - the date of the genetic branching points.

2.3. Summary of archaeogenetics results for ancient Crete and Mycenae

In summary, by the state of the art, may be done the next statements:

- The glacial settlement may have affected both areas and even the entire Aegean region (18-11 thousand years BP).
- The Neolithic (9-8 thousand years BP) settlement reaches Crete from southwestern Anatolia, but the original population is from southeastern Anatolia.
- Mycenae is reached by Neolithic settlement later, but the original population is also came from southeast of Anatolia.
- The glacial genetic heritage is approximately same in both places.
- Considering the approximate time of the prosperity of the Minoan civilization, the steppe immigration (beginning from c. 5,000 BP years) is bypassing both, and even the entire Aegean region too.
- Subsequent historically proven settlements were from related populations because of the small genetic distance between ancient and modern populations.
- From Anatolia to Crete, by coastal shipping and "island-hopping" techniques could even be reached with simple rowing ships of the late Neolithic, for example. With the touch of Rhodes, the greatest offshore distance is only approx. 50km. For such distances not only men who are accustomed to sailing but also the entire population can cross, it is a realistic possibility, and this supposing is necessary for Crete, because of the only masculine Anatolian character is not true, as it is in the case in the Central Mediterranean.

2.4. Questions according to subject for which there is no archaeogenetic answer yet

On the one hand, it is very difficult to obtain samples containing genetic material in the Mediterranean and the Anatolian region, and - on the other hand, the archaeological application of genetic engineering has just begun, so there are many questions to be answered even in our narrow field too:

- It would be good to know what genetic groups consist of the Anatolian and Mesopotamian ancient populations and what their mutual relationship are.

- Thousands of years elapsed between the beginning of Neolithic immigration and the prosperity of the Minoan, so it is logical in itself that during this time more waves of immigrants could reach Crete, but ancient authors (e.g. Homer, Diodorus, Strabon) speak about more Cretan people and more languages are mentioned. To clarify these relationships, it would be useful to know the genetic groups that make up the Cretan ancient population and what their mutual relationship are, and what kind of interacts with the Anatolian groups are.

3. Summary of the encyclopedic knowledge of the regions involved that is more important to our purpose

3.1. Crete and the islands of the nearby Aegean region

3.1.1. Crete

As we have already stated, many Anatolian ethnic groups with agricultural knowledge from the Neolithic to the Bronze Age are likely to be settled in Crete. Now, in chronology, let us look for the last point in time and the distinctive features that a new population may have brought, which has led to the flourishing of Minoan culture.

Chronology

In chronology, we avoid the classification of individual scientists from different perspectives and focus only on events dated by scientific consensus.

Chronology of Minoan Crete

(Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/timeline/>, Febr. 2020)

6000 BCE	First habitation at Malia.
3600 BCE - 3000 BCE	First inhabitation of Phaistos.
3000 BCE	Stone tombs on Crete.
c. 2700 BCE	Olive trees are grown and harvested in Crete. Olive oil is exported.
2200 BCE	First monumental architecture at Malia.
c. 2200 BCE	The Minoan establishes the first navy in the region.
2000 BCE - 1700 BCE	First Minoan palace at Phaistos.
2000 BCE	Minoan hieroglyphic script is invented.
c. 2000 BCE	Pottery wheel introduced to Minoan civilization on Crete.
2000 BCE	The first examples of the lyre in Bronze Age Aegean occur in the Cyclades and on Minoan Crete.
c. 1900 BCE	The first aqueducts were constructed in Mesopotamia and on Minoan Crete
1900 BCE	First Minoan palace at Knossos.
c. 1800 BCE	Minoans on Crete use gold in jewellery manufacture.
1700 BCE	Second Palace of Knossos on Crete.

1700 BCE	Minoan Linear A script.
1700 BCE - 1600 BCE	Second palace at Phaistos.
1675 BCE - 1450 BCE	Second Minoan palace at Malia.
1650 BCE - 1550 BCE	Knossos survives Thera eruption.
c. 1600 BCE	Rhodes has significant contact with Minoan Crete.
c. 1450 BCE	Mycenaen influence extended to Knossos, Crete.
c. 1450 BCE	Destruction of Minoan palace at Zakros.
c. 1450 BCE	Earthquake and fire ends the Minoan period at Malia.

The question is which time point and for what reason should we emphasize to the chronological order?

Already in the Neolithic and early Bronze Age, Cretan people had advanced knowledge of agriculture, crafts and metalworking. The surplus of craft production and the production of bronze, in the absence of local raw materials, are in themselves inducing trade. As Crete is an island, this can only be achieved with advanced shipping. All this requires social organization and administration - that's why the management of the palace and with it the appearance of writing is a key moment. As can be seen in the scientific community this is dated to c. 2200 BCE, and assumed that this sudden change, due to its sudden nature, possible was not a local innovation. The emergence of social organization and division, and the emergence of a ruling aristocracy, have already prevented another elite conflict-free settlement. However, there is no historical trace of such conflict during this period.

Important features and issues and contradictions

- The administrative / power centers and settlements don't have fortified walls. There is no trace of armed rivalry. Later, in culture, there are no signs of 'militarism'. According to their portrayals, society is not male-dominated, female goddesses, fertility and bull cult are important. The mentality of a population can be a lasting characteristic.

- It is an accepted scientific narrative that the Minoan palace-farming society is Knossos-dominated, but there is no clear evidence of this, and it is not even certain that such a power center existed and was on Crete.

- Neither Crete nor Thera, the "most Minoan" town, had archives, diplomatic correspondence, like many other Bronze Age power centers. The management of the palace-economy itself requires administration, and advanced Minoan trade may have been particularly required advanced diplomatic contacts too. Due to the lack of these archives, we may have several assumptions:

- There was one, but all one was destroyed, which is a bit unlikely. If Thera had this, then the lack is understandable, because the only surviving Akrotiri was not a palace center, but a "civilian" city. So if there was one, it would be buried or fell into the caldera along with the palace center.
- The known palace centers were not power centers, and the location of Minoans supposed real power center is not yet known. As a hypothesis to be considered, this real center of power, to the best of our knowledge today, was on Thera, and perhaps destroyed without trace. However, even if this hypothesis is true, it would not explain the lack of administration of the palace

centers. The vassal position of the palace centers, on the other hand, would provide some explanation for the strikingly peaceful relationship with one another, which is unusual at the time.

- The physical destruction of the center of power of a commercialized civilization would be in itself be sufficient explanation for why Minoan Crete was so dramatically affected by the Santorin eruption. While there is no scientific consensus on the devastating impact of eruption on Crete, this indirect effect may be a realistic reason. This relationship also influences the hypotheses concerning the origin of the Minoan aristocracy.

- It also seems plausible narrative that these centers of power represent the same people and populations using the same language. This is far from certain, and according to ancient conditions there would be nothing special about it. The language (s) conveyed by the LA writing system is an agglutinating, certainly non-Indo-European language, such as old-Greek, so despite of the genetic and cultural proximity, the language(s) spoken by the Minoan, was (were) other than Mycenaean.

- We have already stated that the ruling population had to settle, until 2200 BC, however, there is no answer as to when they had to leave the Sumerian land at the latest. An important fact in this regard is that they did not bring the cuneiform with them. Such a clever people would not have left such effective innovation at home.

- Already it is dated to 2200 BC that a Minoan merchant fleet was created. Settling on Crete also assumes a nautical, "non-terrestrial" population, which knowledge has probably been brought with them⁶.

- There are many theories and hypotheses about the direct impact of the Santorin eruption on Crete, but there is no scientific consensus on this issue. One recent theory assumes a gigantic pyroclastic explosion that may have reached Crete (W. Sheppard Baird). However, there is no archaeological evidence yet. The tsunami hypothesis is very popular. W. Sheppard Baird pointed out in articles [8] [10] that this is unsustainable using with a GIS model based on study [9] (Hendrik J. Bruins et al). However, the tsunami, whose existence has been archaeologically proven, though not a fatal disaster, could have caused serious damage. Coastal settlements and commercial depots, harbors could be destroyed, both in Crete and the Cyclades [9] [11]. Similarly, it is very possible, the merchant and military fleets also destroyed. The Minoan people were a peaceful people on the mainland, but the use of the stabbing nose is indicative of the existence of a military fleet. It is believed that this was used to protect the island's coastline. Human, commercial, and military damage may have been great, but so could the Anatolian rivals, so the loss of commercial superiority or the supposed Anatolian invasion is not realistic as a direct consequence of the disaster. However, if it was not an immediate effect that caused the decline, then it must be taken into account that the loss of Thera, because of its importance and the nature of its potential center, would have been much greater. If so, the construction and origin of the Minoan "empire" must be different imagine.

- It is striking and no reasonable explanation can be found as to why the management of the palaces extend only to the eastern half of the island and this did not cause conflicts. As I mentioned, even the ancient authors speak of "original Crete" (Eteocretan). However, one very important thing to keep in mind regarding these sources is that these authors were all alive in the classical Greek era, and from their perspective all of peoples lived there before Mycenaean and Doric dominance were all "original

⁶ Unlike the Mycenaean, who were originally "land peoples" and when they arrived on today's Greek mainland, they already found a Minoan dominance in the Aegean islands.

Cretan". The ruins of Karfi are an eclectic example for this, which is known as the refuge of the original Cretans, although it is located to the east region, south of Malia and not to the west of the island.

3.1.2. Minoan effects in the Aegean Islands Chronologies

Chronology of Cyclades

(Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/timeline/>, Febr. 2020)

c. 5000 BCE	The Cyclades are first inhabited by settlers from Asia Minor.
3000 BCE - 2200 BCE	The first archaeological evidence of organised communities in the Cyclades.
3000 BCE - 2000 BCE	Distinctive minimalistic standing marble figurines are produced in the Cyclades.
3000 BCE - 2000 BCE	First rock-cut burial chambers at Akrotiri.
2700 BCE - 2300 BCE	The first depiction in art of the aulos musical instrument appears in Cycladic sculpture.
2200 BCE - 1700 BCE	Evidence of town planning and more sophisticated architecture in the Cyclades.
2000 BCE - 1650 BCE	Akrotiri on Thera reaches its peak of prosperity and becomes a flourishing Mediterranean trading centre.
1650 BCE - 1550 BCE	Eruption of <u>Thera</u> and consequent tidal waves, destruction of <u>Akrotiri</u> and other <u>Aegean</u> centres.

Chronology of Akrotiri

(Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/timeline/>, Febr. 2020)

c. 4500 BCE	First settlement on Thera.
3000 BCE - 2000 BCE	First rock-cut burial chambers at Akrotiri.
c. 2000 BCE	Akrotiri becomes an important Aegean trading centre.
2000 BCE - 1650 BCE	Akrotiri on Thera reaches its peak of prosperity and becomes a flourishing Mediterranean trading centre.
1650 BCE - 1550 BCE	Eruption of Thera and consequent tidal waves, destruction of Akrotiri and other Aegean centres.

Chronology of Rhodes

(Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/timeline/>, Febr. 2020)

c. 1600 BCE	Rhodes has significant contact with Minoan Crete.
1510 BCE	The traditional date Danaos builds a temple to Athena Lindia at Lindus on Rhodes.

Chronology of Mycenaen

(Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/timeline/>, Febr. 2020)

c. 6000 BCE - 2900 BCE	Neolithic Age settlements in Greece, beginning of agriculture.
2300 BCE	Bronze is used in the Aegean.

2000 BCE	Early Greeks settle the Peloponnese.
c. 1450 BCE	Mycenaean monumental architecture first appears at Epidaurus.

Important features

- The palace-economy and the planned cities appeared almost simultaneously in Crete, Thera⁷ and the Cyclades. It is not necessarily of Cretan origin.
- In the Cyclades, with the exception of Thera, the Minoan effect is unambiguous (archaeological evidence), but not dominant, the original Cycladic and Anatolian characteristics are continuous.
- In the nearby Rhodes and Cyprus, there is traces of Minoan trade and trade depots, but no dominance.
- In Mycenae, the findings of the numerous Minoan commercial products prove the lively relationship, but the Minoan influence is limited to that. Mycenae palace-economy appeared approx. 500 years later.

3.2. Southern Mesopotamia

Chronology

We have previously stated that Crete and the Cyclades may have been settled by numerous Anatolian ethnic groups with agricultural knowledge from the Neolithic to the Bronze Age. Here again, in the chronology, we look for the last probably time point and key distinctions we have outlined previously. We look for the dominant population that had crossed Anatolia for some centuries had brought about the flourishing of Minoan culture.

Chronology of Uruk

(Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/timeline/>, Febr. 2020)

c. 5400 BCE	The City of Eridu is founded.
c. 5000 BCE	Sumer inhabited by Ubaid people.
4500 BCE	First walled cities. Uruk in Mesopotamia first city.
c. 4500 BCE	The City of Uruk founded.
4100 BCE - 2900 BCE	Uruk Period in Mesopotamia. First cities.
4100 BCE - 2900 BCE	Uruk Period in Sumer.
4100 BCE - 2900 BCE	Mesopotamian science and technology first appears in the Uruk Period of Sumer.
c. 4000 BCE	Creation at Uruk of first mass-produced bowls.
c. 3600 BCE	Invention of writing in Sumer at Uruk.
c. 3200 BCE	First instance of written language in Sumerian.
2900 BCE - 2334 BCE	The Early Dynastic Period in Sumer.

⁷ Thera has limited archaeological material caused by the eruption - compared to what was supposed may have been there. Even so, the development and richness of Akrotiri is impressive even in respect to Crete. It is difficult to decide whether this superiority was the case in the Bronze Age or whether only there was not a pumice coverage on Crete that preserved this splendor and sophistication.

c. 2600 BCE	Uruk ruled by Gilgamesh for 126 years according to the Sumerian King List.
2100 BCE	First ziggurats in Ur, Eridu, Uruk, and Nippur.
2100 BCE	The Reign of Utu-Hegal at Uruk in Sumer and creation of Sumerian King List.
c. 2055 BCE - 2047 BCE	Utu Hegel's reign over Sumerian and Akkadian cities.
2047 BCE - 1750 BCE	The Ur III Period in Sumer. Great Wall of Uruk still standing.
1787 BCE	Hammurabi of Babylon conquers Uruk and Isin.

Chronology of Cuneiform in Uruk

(Leo Oppenheim, Ancient Mesopotamia: portrait of a dead civilization, 1977, Chicago University Press)

• Protosumer pictograms	(35 - 31st century BC)
• Sumerian pictograms	(31st - 29th centuries BC)
• Sumerian proto- cuneiform	(30th-25th century BC)
• Elam script	(from the 30th century BC)
• Sumerian cuneiform	(26th to 9th century BC)
• Akkadian cuneiform	(25th to 17th centuries BC)

Important features

The first Neolithic farmers in Europe could probably come from the Halaf and Hassuna-Samarra cultures. (Figure 1)

Typically in this culture, e.g. in Çatal Höyük, female gods, cult bull representations refer to the cult of fertility, and women and men have equal social status. This attitude would be typical of the Early Neolithic Aegean and Europe cultures (M. Gimbutas - "original European") [12].

Figure 1: Map of Mesopotamia c. 6000. BC. (Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/map/>, Feb. 2020)

As stated previously, immigrants defining Minoan civilization were members of a population having advanced agricultural, craftsmanship, commercial, architectural, and nautical knowledge, but did not yet know / apply cuneiform, only the preceding hieroglyphic / pictographic writing system. These conditions are fulfilled by the Uruk culture [13]:

- In the 4th millennium the irrigation agriculture with plow use was formed in the lower part of Tigris–Euphrates river system.
- The first walled cities were built and the first forms of palace-economy and church-state were formed.
- Metal craftsmanship appears which generates commerce due to the lack of local raw materials and necessitates the use of writing.
- The towns of Eridu, Uruk, Ur are situated on the Euphrates coast, near the Persian Gulf, which has much higher water level and less well-filled at that time (Figure 2). In addition to inland trade, they maintain maritime links with the Indus Valley and the northern coast of East Africa, and even their traders reach the Mediterranean. This includes nautical experience and geographic knowledge. Uruk products can also be found in Anatolia, Iran, Indus Valley, Levant and Egypt.
- Uruk began to decline during the Jemdet Nasr Period (about 3100-2900 BC) of the Northern Mesopotamian origin, and in this time the archaeological strata suggest significant depopulation.
- The early c. 3600 BC formed pictographic writings (Uruk, Kis archaic texts) conveyed some kind of Protosumer language, while the first writing that is sure to convey Sumerian language is from the Jemdet Nasr Period, approx. 31st century BC, which language probably was not spoken by these migrants. It is also probable that the emigrants were not yet influenced by later Sumerian or Akkadian cultural influences, but represented a Protosumer culture. Assuming the Sumerian is a descendant of the Protosumer, there are some things that may have been true:

- It was probably an agglutinating “island language”.
- Its case system is ergative, which is the language represents the subject of the unbiased verb and the subject in the same case, and the subject of the objective verb in the same case.
- The northern boundary of the Protosumer language area was at the height of the city of Nippur and stretched south to the then Persian Gulf.

- The temple of Kulaba city was dedicated to the goddess An, while the temple of the city of Eanna was the residence of the goddess of love and fertility. Signs of the Uruk seal rolls attest to the bull cult. The bull, the symbol of the god An and then Enlil, is the bearer of fertility. This is the Neolithic Anatolian heritage.

Figure 2: Map of Mesopotamia c. 3100. BC. (Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/map/>, Feb. 2020)

Summary of important features

Summarizing the above: - population defining the Minoan culture c. 3100 BC, it may have been a merchant-sailing nation (s) living in the Uruk culture, speaking Protosumer languages, and using the Uruk pictographic writing system, probably settled on the southern and then southwestern coasts of Anatolia and then migrated (some parts) to the Cyclades and Crete. As the Akkadian empire extended to the southeastern Anatolian coast in 2200 BC (Figure 3), it is certain that the last settlers could only come from the west, southwestern coast, since there is no trace of the Akkadian influence on Crete⁸.

⁸ According to the legend of the Akkadian king Sarrukin (2300 - 2215 BC), the king conquered Kaptara (Crete) [14]. However, on the one hand, he only mentions Kaptara itself, while later texts that list the glorious deeds of the dynasty are already about Kaptara Island. However, during this era, several Kaptara's were known, on the one hand Kaptara was every Cretan commercial depot (like today "Chinatown") and on the other hand, in Southern Anatolia, there was also a city known as Kaptara, which was probably only a commercial depot as well. So Sarrukin's original naming may have been referring to this repository only. Incidentally, such a conquest was, at that time, logically unimaginable for the essentially mainland Akkadian people. Another problem is that the supposed "Akkadian invasion" in Crete has no archaeological evidence.

This is in line with our prior assumption for the culture, mentality and religion of the population.

However, it should be noted that the original designation "Sumer Origin Theory" (SOT) may be changed to "Uruk Origin Theory" (UOT).

Figure 3: Map of Mesopotamia c. 2200. BC. (Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/map/>, Feb. 2020)

3.3 South, Southwest Anatolia

One of a late Uruk population in range of c. 3100 - 2200 BC reached Crete and Thera. For a period of approx. 900 years, presumably living and moving in southern Anatolia, in contact with the original Neolithic population, exposed to cultural influences. Therefore, we need to consider the peoples, proto-states / centers of power with which they could have come in contact. These contacts had an impact on their language and writing system, which in itself could have changed a lot in 900 years.

3.3.1. The Problem of Anatolia's Encyclopedic Narrative

There is no scientific consensus date system for Anatolia's chronology. Usually eras are established on the basis of Trojan exploration layers, but this is not generally accepted. There are few finds and even fewer written references (early retrospectively) about the early Bronze Age. All we can do is try to trace back data from later times to peoples, languages, centers of power.

Power centers, regions

Figure 4: Map of Anatolia c. 1500. BC. (Created by <https://www.ancient.eu/map/>, Feb. 2020)

Figure 5: Map of Anatolia c. 1200. BC. (Near_East_topographic_map-blank.svg; Schemhur, Al-qamar, 2013)

It can be seen that on the map of 1500 BC (Figure 4) there are only two regions of interest to us, Arzawa and Lukka, then on the map around 1200 BC (Figure 5), additional region information is included, e.g. important cities such as Wilusa (Vilusa), Apasa (Ephesus), Millawanda (Miletus), Avarna (Xanthosz, Kınık) [15]. The southeastern region of Anatolia can be excluded because it had a strong Akkadian and later Hittite influence, which cannot be detected in Minoan culture. So the regions that matter to us are:

- Arzawa (later Lycia) as a power region dates from 1500 BC and its capital was Apasa (c. 7000 BC). Probably had a close relationship with Wilusa, whose capital was Taruisa (later Troas / Troad / Troy), whose first layer can be dated to 3000 BC. The borders between Arzawa and Lukka are uncertain.
- Lukka (Luqqa, Lycia), whose an important independent region was later Karkiya / Caria, whose capital was Milas, then Halikarnassos (Bodrum). It is difficult to place the Luwi language area, or possibly the ruler center (if it existed), because otherwise it is placed in the Lower Hatti area, but the Luwi effect appears throughout Anatolia. Some scholars place the Luwiya / Luwa region in common area of Arzawa and Lukka, which does not match the language region.

Southwestern Anatolian peoples and languages

There is even greater uncertainty regarding peoples and languages than in identifying regions. Luvic peoples (Luwians) and languages (Common Luwian / Proto-Luwian / ... / Luvic group - Melchert, 2012) are located in the affected Anatolian area, as are the narrowly interpreted Luwi (Luwian), Carian, lyc (Lycian), and Sidetic. The other Luvic peoples / languages are all placed to the inner or eastern areas of Anatolia [15] [16] [17].

3.3.2. The "Luwi Theory"

It has been repeatedly raised by many scholars since the early 2000s, but since Melchert's suggestion in 2012, it has been accepted by the profession that Luwi languages are a large group and are widely distributed, except for the northeastern region of Anatolia, and kind of version of Luwi were spoke. Thus, contrary to the old hypothesis, it was not a Hittite dialect, but a common language of the empire, while the Hatti could have been the language of aristocracy and diplomacy. There is also a widespread view that besides linguistic kinship there is a cultural similarity [17].

Swiss geo-archaeologist Eberhard Zangger founded the Luwian Studies Foundation in 2014 [18] and in 2016 published a highly debated⁹ book on "Luwi civilization" [19]. The purpose of the foundation is to support bronze and Iron Age archeological research in Western Anatolia. As part of this, the foundation has systematically cataloged more than 340 large Middle and Late Bronze Age settlements in western Asia (Figure 6). The details of these sites are published on their website and the database is publicly accessible.

Figure 6: Bronze Age Tell - Eskişehir, Google Map (Feb 2020)

Zangger also points out that much of the excavation so far stops at the Greek-Roman strata, which is understandable, but that we know nothing about pre-Iron and Bronze Age settlements, and on the other

⁹ The intense professional controversy was caused by Zangger's suggestion that the Luwian culture of Western Anatolian Nations at the beginning of the 13th century BC, they allied and first defeated their ancient enemies, the Hittites, and after seeing the expansion of the Achaean to Mycenae and to Crete, and fearing to continue this, they turned against the Achaean Alliance, thus triggering the "World War 0". The last act of this long war is the so-called "Trojan War". Zangger identifies the Luwian alliance with the mysterious sea peoples. Some researchers disagree with the hypothesis of the existence of the alleged Luwi Alliance and deny their identity with the sea peoples.

hand, many ancient settlements are still inhabited today, so the possibility of exploration is very limited and adventitious. Therefore, the research of the discovered ancient tells would be of great importance. Another important opportunity would be to get acquainted with the archeogenetic history and map of Anatolia. To find out e.g. the relationship between the first Neolithic farmers and Bronze Age populations.

Except for the indignation of the profession of historian, the introduction of the "Luwi civilization" [20] as a separate category may help to better understand Anatolia's very complex ancient history.

Figure 7: The extent of "Luwi civilization" according to Luwian Studies [20]

The Luwi language

Regardless of whether or not the existence of a unified Luwi culture and linguistic group is accepted, the following encyclopedic features are accepted for Luwi-type languages before the Hittite era:

- Luwi languages are a subgroup of the Anatolian group of the Indo-European language family.
- Their culture and languages, their proto-Anatolian language was formed by a mixture of Neolithic, non-Indo-European populations, and later immigrated Indo-European (Caucasian) peoples (c. 4000 BC).
- The main spread of the Luwi language is classically limited to the territory of Kizzuwatna, whereas according to Luwi theory, the languages of the Luwi group were ubiquitous except in Northeastern Anatolia.

Luwi Hieroglyphics [LH]

The writing system of the Luwi language is regarded as an endemic hieroglyphic syllable. Unfortunately, according to current archaeological material, their earliest occurrence is currently only found on stamp presses dating back to 2000 BC. Later Hittite-Luwi inscriptions and texts (1400 BC) helped to interpret the writing system, but it also became clear that it was a language and writing quite different from the Hittite. Consequently, the phonetic correspondence of syllables is also controversial.

Following the summative work of Melchert, H. Craig, and James Mellaart¹⁰, Fred C. Woudhuizen (also working with Luwian Studies) as a relevant expert on Luwi languages and scripts in [21], taking account of the Luwi scripts, he states that it is clearly excluded that the Luwi scripts were Hittite, having been widely used in Western Anatolia since around 2000 BC. So the Luwi scripts are endemic, self-innovating, closely related writing systems of Neolithic and early Indo-European immigrants. Future excavations in Anatolia will probably provide objective evidence of this.

The Luwi-Minos, Sumer-Minos relationships

Already during the first LH-CH comparisons, pictographic similarities emerged and the LH-CH relationship was extensively studied. In Zangger's summary book [19], citing Leonard Robert Palmer ("Mycenaeans and Minoans" - 1961) and other authors, back until 1928, he draws attention not only to the notices for Luwi-Minoan relationship, but also to the language relations of Luwi-Greek.

In 1961 Leonard R. Palmer hypothesized that LA could be considered Luwian. Margalit Finkelberg states in 2005 that Crete may have been colonized by a Southwestern Anatolian population - and that the Minoan language may have evolved from one of the languages of the Luwi region, but there is a scientific consensus based on very few short scripts that the fundamental language of Minoan is not Luwian. Luwi relatedness can be discovered, especially in the similarity of the pictographic elements of the scripts.

Although there are very few scripts to "decode" the Minoan language, existing scripts must be treated with strict "source criticism". A typical example of this is the already originality disputed Phaistos disc. There are countless "decipherments", but in 2016 Zangger [19] published a concerted, seemingly relevant narrative based on the independent results of Jan Best and Fred Woudhuizen Dutch linguists. According to them, the disc is a replica of a possession plaque that around 1350 BC, it was produced in several copies, in the transitional period of Mycenae, in the "diplomatic" workshop of the King of Arzawa in Apasa, in the Luwian language of Arzawa. However, even though this reading seems most relevant in terms of both its method and function, no "solution" can be considered as long as the Greek authorities do not permit physical examination of the disc material, the origin of the clay and the time of its preparation are proved. The example of the disc shows the first question whether the script was written in Minoan or in Cretan at all?

Without denying the obvious luwi effect, in 2015 authors of article [22] were not the first to state that neither CH nor LA is suitable for writing a single Indo-European (e.g. Luwian) language in around of Crete, - that is why they suggest a proto-script created for an archaic form of the Sumer should be

¹⁰ Counterfeiting scandal: Following the death of James Mellaart in 2012, his son and Swiss-German geo-archaeologist Eberhard Zangger published in 2018 a report (Luwian Studies, Media Release) stating that Mellaart had found many fakes in support of his thesis. After inspecting the documentation in Mellaart's apartment, Zangger discovered that Mellaart had altered many of the ancient mural paintings, and probably operated a kind of "counterfeit workshop". In other respects, his work of the profession acknowledges.

identified. They in their 2017 article [23] proposed a Cretan Protolinear (CP) archaic Sumerian writing format from which the Aegean scripts may have evolved.

4. Summary, reasonings, conclusions

Summarizing the statements listed in the previous paragraphs:

- Around 9000 years ago, in several waves, early agricultural populations of eastern Anatolia migrated to the Aegean and then to the northern Mediterranean and to the present-day Europe. Historically, there have been many populations in Crete.
- Around 3100 BC, depopulation of the areas of the Uruk civilization occurs and a population of high agricultural, commercial, artisanal, and nautical culture settles on the coast of southern Anatolia. Their language is proto-Sumerian, their writing system may have been pictographic, and they have not yet used cuneiform. In their commercial activities they reach Crete, Thera and the Cyclades islands as their culture and writing system evolve with neighboring Luwi peoples, but the nature of their language does not change.
- Around 2200 BC, the social structure of Crete is suddenly changing with appearing the palace economies and the Minoan influence is intensifying on the islands of the Cyclades. The appearance of an aristocratic society is also crucial because it prevents the incoming of another external force, so this phenomenon can be used as a chronological dating.
- The Cretan palace economies are strikingly peaceful with one another. The mutual relationship between human groups is determined by the civilization mentality, but above all by competition or struggle for access to limited resources. Although we do not know the sizes of the populations dominated by palace economies, it seems unlikely that such conflicts would not have occurred. The fact that there are no traces of internal wars may indicate that this was curbed by an external, dominant force and resolved conflicts between subordinate parties.
- Despite the huge Minoan trade relations, there is very little remaining of "diplomatic correspondence" in the ruins of palace economies. For example, it is only after Thera's destruction that the "ambassadors" of Crete (Keftiu) appear on the Egyptian inscriptions with typical objects known from Akrotiri. The geological effects of the Santorini eruption could have equally affected the entire Aegean region, so the catastrophe could not bring the rival Anatolian city-states to a decisive competitive advantage, but in spite of this Crete is rapidly declining and peace between palace economies is disappearing. It is worth addressing the possibility that, in addition to the material casualties of the disaster, the loss of the trading system may have been the most serious cause of the crisis, because the real center and owner was not Crete, but Thera. This would represent a whole new structure of the Minoan world and would explain many mysteries.
- Neither the language behind CH nor LA was closely related to any of nearby language, but not even the Sumerian known by Akkadian. The approx. 900-year-old journey in the Uruk-Crete-Thera, Luwi environment may be an explanation, because the proto Sumerian changed from the Luwi influences is not the same as the late Sumerian or any Luwi language, and the same is true for the writing system, which was applied separately for every languages. Further question is how many Minoan languages existed and they were dialects or independent languages?
- Because there are very few archaeological finds and scripts from time Minoan-Luwi coexistence before 2200 BC, only the joint evaluation of a later set of Arzawa, Lukka and Minoan scripts can be used to distinguish a CP signal group, which is the archive of an archaic Sumerian

writing system. This writing system is carried by the proto Sumer settlers, who flourished Thera, Crete and built up the Minoan empire.

- One question remains open and its significance is difficult to judge: why are the palace economies extended to the eastern part of Crete only?

In 2019, in an article by Evangelos C. Papakitsos [24], there was a much narrower timeline for the arrival of the "Sumerian settlers", that is 2800-2600 BC, however neither the time and cause of immigration nor the date of migration to Crete seem to be sufficiently substantiated, and the time frame seems too narrow. I consider the reasons and time frame presented in this article to be more relevant, and the broader timeline noted also explains coevolution with the Luwi civilization, which is an undeniable fact.

Although the possibilities outlined in this article are still quite broad for some paleographic studies, it has to be accepted that further narrowing cannot be done due to the supposed historical background.

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